

The Influence Of *Gross Npf* , *Mudharabah Income*, And *Wadiah Bonus* On Receipt Of *Ziswaf Funds* With *Firm Size* As A Moderation Variable In Sharia Banking In Indonesia For The Period of 2018 - 2023

Zulaikhatul Khuluddiyah
Universitas Islam Negeri Maulana Malik Ibrahim Malang, Indonesia
zulaikhatul@gmail.com

Abstract

This research aims to examine the influence of Gross NPF, Mudharabah Income, and Wadiah Bonus on ZISWAF Fund Receipts, with Firm Size as a moderating variable. The research sample consisted of 115 data for 6 years from 5 Sharia Banks selected using purposive sampling. Data analysis was carried out using Panel Data Regression Analysis and Moderated Regression Analysis (MRA) with the Eviews 12 application. The research results showed that NPF Gross had no significant effect on ZISWAF Fund Receipts. Mudharabah income shows a significant negative effect, which means that an increase in mudharabah income can reduce ZISWAF fund receipts, and vice versa. The Wadiah Bonus, on the other hand, indicates a significant positive influence, meaning that increasing the Wadiah bonus can increase ZISWAF fund receipts. In the context of moderation, company size does not moderate the influence of Gross NPF on ZISWAF fund receipts. However, company size is able to moderate the influence of mudharabah income and wadiah bonuses on ZISWAF fund receipts.

Keywords: *Gross NPF* , *Mudharabah Income*, *Wadiah Bonus*, *ZISWAF Fund Receipts*, and *Firm Size*

1. INTRODUCTION

Sharia banks are financial institutions that operate and present products that are in line with the principles of the Koran and hadith, especially in terms of Islamic transaction ethics. Mit Gamr Bank, founded in 1963, in Egypt, was an important starting point in the growth of Islamic banking globally. Then, in 1975, Dubai Islamic Bank was a pioneer as a commercial bank that was the first to offer sharia-based services. Various sharia banking models have been positively received in Indonesia since the approval of Law No. 21 of 2008 which explains sharia banking. Bank Indonesia regulations covering technical aspects of sharia banking based on this law. Many believe that with the sharia banking law, there will be an increase in investment which will strengthen the position of sharia banking in the country (Ghozali et al., 2019).

With the majority of Indonesia's population adhering to Islam, the sharia banking industry in this country continues to develop. Indonesia's Islamic banking sector recorded a marked increase in 2020, with Islamic financial assets potentially reaching 99 billion, making it one of the largest in the world as the fourth largest (Nurhayati et al., 2021). The presence of sharia banks in Indonesia is expected to bring positive benefits and contribute to the welfare of Muslims (Mulyani & Juniamawarni, 2024). Sharia commercial banks have three main focuses, namely collecting funds from the community, distributing funds and

providing services. In raising funds, two main contracts are used, namely the wadi'ah and mudharabah contracts(Hartono, 2019)

Savings products with wadiah contracts are increasingly in demand by the public because they are considered one of the many types of Islamic bank savings that offer convenience. In this type of savings, if the customer's savings balance increases from the initial balance, the customer's savings will not decrease. This balance increase usually comes from bonuses given by the bank. Even though banks have full rights and responsibilities for customer funds in wadiah savings, banks generally provide these benefits in the form of bonuses to customers. This wadiah savings bonus is obtained from the profits obtained by sharia banks from their operations in generating funds, including operational income from financing and investment funds. The hope of providing this bonus is to motivate people to be more interested in saving at sharia banks and can be an indicator of banking business performance. The bigger the bonus given, the better the banking performance, because it indicates that the bank's income also increases, which then has a positive impact on the wadiah savings bonus given to customers (Sari, 2021).

Mudharabah financing is one of the most popular financing options in sharia banks. Annual sharia banking data in 2012 indicates this. Data provided by Bank Indonesia shows that distribution of funds in the form of dominance dominates, reaching 78.72%. This indirectly affects the profitability of Sharia Commercial Banks (Maulana & Yunita, 2020). Apart from bringing profits, mudharabah financing also has potential risks, such as the possibility of problematic financing (NPF) (Zaidan, 2019). During the 2015-2019 period, the NPF value at Sharia Commercial Banks experienced winter. Unstable customer business conditions can cause NPF to arise. Internal and external factors related to banks also play a role in moving NPF (Safitri et al., 2020).

Sharia banking displays unique characteristics that differentiate it from conventional banks, where apart from acting as a financial intermediary, sharia banks also have social obligations. One aspect of the social obligations of Islamic banks is fund management ZISWAF (Zakat, Infaq, Alms, Grants and Waqf) and its distribution to zakat management institutions. This social function is regulated in Law No. 21 of 2008 concerning Sharia Banking which states that sharia banks and Sharia Business Units (UUS) can carry out social obligations through the Baitul Mal institution. The task of this institution is to receive funds from these sources and allocate them to the ZISWAF management organization or other social funds.(Nurnasrina & Adiyes, 2021).

The management and utilization of ZISWAF Funds has great significance in advancing the economy and empowering society, especially in Indonesia. ZISWAF funds play an important role in improving welfare and reducing poverty, as well as supporting the efficiency of zakat as a form of productive social charity (Anjelina et al., 2020). In this context, Gross NPF, Mudharabah Income, and Wadiah Bonus are important factors that influence ZISWAF Fund income. Gross NPF as an indicator of strong economic prosperity, Mudharabah Income as a profitable form of investment for capital providers and the community, and Wadiah Bonus as a stimulant for customer behavior in saving in sharia banking, all play a role in increasing the potential for zakat funds that can be collected and distributed.

This research is devoted to determining the impact of Gross NPF, Mudharabah Income, and Wadiah Bonus on ZISWAF Fund receipts with Firm Size as a Moderating Variable, from the period 2018.Q1 to 2023.Q3. By considering these moderating variables, the focus of this research is to explore how *company size* can influence the relationship between these factors and the receipt of ZISWAF Funds, as well as how the interaction between these variables can influence the management and use of ZISWAF Funds in Indonesia.

Through this research, it is hoped that new insights can be gained regarding how NPF Gross, Mudharabah Income, and Wadiah Bonus which are moderated by Firm Size influence the receipt of ZISWAF funds, as well as how this can be used as a basis for a more effective and effective strategy for managing and using ZISWAF Funds. efficient .

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Gross NPF

According to Purba (2022)NPF, it is a metric used to assess a bank's ability to manage financing that is experiencing problems, which currently cannot be repaid using productive assets owned by the bank. NPF reflects credit that is late in payment and does not meet the minimum payment obligations that have been determined. NPF itself can be divided into two, namely *gross NPF* and *net NPF* . The difference between the two lies in the PPAP (Handling of Productive Asset Write-Offs) in the calculation. *Gross NPF* does not take PPAP into account, while *net NPF* considers PPAP in its calculations. The higher the NPF level, the higher the level of problematic financing, which also indicates low quality in the financing distribution process by Islamic banks (Yokoyama & Mahardika, 2019).

Mudharabah Income

According to Roni (2021)mudharabah income is the result obtained from a business that is financed to another party to improve their business, through a cooperation agreement where one side becomes the capital provider (shohibul maal) and the other side manages the business (mudharib).

Wadiah Bonus

According to Sari (2021)Wadiah Bonus, it is a financial imbalance from the bank to customers or clients as appreciation for placing their funds in wadiah savings. The determination of this bonus is not predetermined and depends entirely on bank policy. The hope of providing this bonus is to motivate people to be more interested in saving at sharia banks and can be an indicator of banking business performance. The bigger the bonus given to customers, the more efficiently the funds are allocated to investments that generate profits.

Receipt of ZISWAF Funds

According to Mufrodi (2022)Ziswaf, it is an abbreviation of Zakat, Infaq, Alms, and Waqf, which are several social financial tools in Islam that aim to empower the people. They can be used as a basis for supporting the growth of the socio-economic strength of society as part of efforts to achieve national development. Receipt of ZISWAF funds at sharia banks is income obtained from the collection of zakat isiwa funds (ZISWAF) received by sharia banks. ZISWAF is zakat received by sharia banks and used for Islamic social activities.

Company Size

According to Krisnando & Novitasari, (2021)Company size, also known as company size, is a parameter that indicates the financial stability of a company. This reflects the dimensions or scale of the company which refers to sales revenue and the total assets it owns. The greater the number of assets owned by a corporate entity, the larger the size of the company.

Hypothesis Development

Effect of Gross NPF on ZISWAF Fund Receipts (H₁)

According to Hadi (2021) hypothesis testing of the relationship between Non-Performing Financing (NPF) and Zakat, it indicates agreement with the hypothesis because the probability value exceeds 0.05, namely 0.4221. A high or low NPF value does not really affect the bank's ability to earn profits, so the NPF ratio may not affect Islamic banks in zakat.

Influence of Mudharabah Income on ZISWAF Fund Receipts (H₂)

According to Wirawan et al. (2022) Mudharabah Income, as a form of investment that involves giving capital in the hope of making a profit, it can be considered as a way to manage and return zakat funds in a way that is profitable for both the capital provider and the community who receive benefits from the funds. In the context of ZISWAF Fund management, the use of Mudharabah Income can have a positive impact on economic development and community empowerment. This is because Mudharabah Income can create innovations in the management of zakat funds, such as investing in projects that are profitable for the community and returning capital with significant profits. This can increase the receipt of ZISWAF Funds and enable the use of zakat funds for productive activities, such as providing training for home industries, providing business capital, and providing scholarships to support quality education, as part of contributing to the development of educated human resources for the nation .

The Effect of Wadiah Bonuses on ZISWAF Fund Receipts (H₃)

According to research, Novianto (2021) Gross Domestic Product (GDP) income and the wadiah savings bonus level have a positive impact on wadiah savings in the short term. However, in the long term, GDP and the level of wadiah savings bonuses indicate a negative impact on Wadiah Savings in Islamic banks in Indonesia. Even though it indirectly discusses the influence of Wadiah Bonuses on ZISWAF Fund Receipts, this research shows that the level of bonuses can influence customer behavior in saving in sharia banking, which in turn can have an impact on the management and use of zakat funds, including ZISWAF Funds. This is because sharia banking is often a source of zakat funds, and customer behavior in saving can influence the amount of funds collected and distributed.

Gross NPF on ZISWAF Fund Receipts is moderated by *firm size* (H₄)

Company Size Refers to the size of the company's total assets, which includes all physical and non-physical assets owned by the company. The size of the company can influence how the company can manage and use zakat funds, especially in terms of investment and development. The effect of *Gross NPF* on ZISWAF Fund Receipts moderated by company size can be interpreted as how the economic welfare of a country (as measured by *Gross NPF*) influences the way companies manage and use zakat funds, taking into account the size of their company. For example, larger companies may have the capacity to manage zakat funds more effectively and efficiently, which could increase ZISWAF Fund receipts (Katharina et al., 2022).

The influence of Mudharabah Income on ZISWAF Fund Receipts is moderated by *company size* (H₅)

Mudharabah financing affects the financial performance of sharia banking, which can be interpreted as an indicator of how the management and use of zakat funds, including ZISWAF Funds, can influence economic development and community empowerment. Mudharabah income, as a form of income from sharia financing, can

influence ZISWAF Fund income through the company or organization that manages the fund. Company size (*firm size*) can influence the extent to which the company can manage and use mudharabah funds effectively, which in turn can influence the amount of zakat funds collected and distributed (Yuliana, 2021).

The influence of Wadiah Bonus on ZISWAF Fund Receipts is moderated by *firm size* (H₆)

Wadiah Bonuses can be considered as one way to manage and return zakat funds in a way that is profitable for both the capital provider and the community who receive benefits from these funds (Suryani & Fitriani, 2022). The Wadiah Bonus can be considered as one way to maximize the benefits of the zakat funds collected and distributed. In the influence of Wadiah Bonuses on ZISWAF Fund Receipts which is moderated by *company size* , it can be interpreted that company size can influence the extent to which Wadiah Bonuses can be given and used to manage and return zakat funds. Companies with a larger size scale may have more potential to arrange Wadiah Bonuses, which in turn can increase the receipt of ZISWAF Funds.

Gross NPF , Mudharabah Income, and Wadiah Bonus on ZISWAF Fund Receipts (H₇)

Overall *Gross NPF* , Mudharabah Income, and Wadiah Bonus function as stimulants that can influence ZISWAF Fund income. They play a role in improving economic welfare, managing and returning zakat funds in a profitable way, as well as influencing customer behavior in saving in sharia banking, which ultimately can influence the amount of zakat funds collected and distributed.

The hypothesis the researcher proposes is related to the argument above, namely:

- H1: Effect of Gross NPF on ZISWAF Fund Receipts.
- H2: Effect of Mudharabah Income on ZISWAF Fund Receipts.
- H3: Effect of Wadiah Bonus on Receipt of ZISWAF Funds.
- H4: The influence of *Gross NPF* on ZISWAF Fund Receipts is moderated by *company size*.
- H5: The influence of Mudharabah Income on ZISWAF Fund Receipts is moderated by *company size*.
- H6: The effect of Wadiah Bonus on ZISWAF Fund Receipts is moderated by *company size*.
- H7: The effect of Wadiah Bonus on ZISWAF Fund Receipts is moderated by *company size*.

Figure 1. Framework of Thought

Source: Compiled by the author (2024)

3. RESEARCH METHODS

This research uses quantitative research methods with a regression analysis approach. The data selected is secondary data obtained from financial reports of Sharia Banking, the Financial Services Authority, and statistics provided by related statistical

agencies. Research objects include Bank Muamalat, Bank Syariah Indonesia, Bank Victoria Syariah, Bank Mega Syariah, and Bank Panin Dubai Syariah. The research time span is from the first quarter of 2018 to the third quarter of 2023. The research population includes the five Islamic banks mentioned previously, while the data sample will be selected purposively. The total sample used was 115 observations. This research applies a Panel Data Regression Model and Moderated Regression Analysis (MRA). Panel data regression models combine cross-time data (*time series*) and *cross-sectional* data , while Moderated Regression Analysis (MRA) considers the influence of moderator variables on the relationship between independent and dependent variables. Interaction tests, or Moderated Regression Analysis, provide a framework for highlighting the influence of moderator variables in a regression model.

The following is the model equation in panel data regression analysis:

$$Y = \alpha + \beta_1X_1 + \beta_2X_2 + \beta_3X_3 + e_i$$

Where:

Y = Receipt of Ziswaf funds

α = Constant

β = Regression Coefficient

X₁ = gross NPF

X₂ = Mudharabah income

X₃ = Wadiah Bonus

e_i = Error

In this research, hypothesis testing was carried out using regression analysis with the moderating variable Moderating Regression Analysis (MRA). The regression equation used involves interaction elements, and the formula is as follows:

$$Y = \alpha + \beta_1X_1 + \beta_2X_2 + \beta_3X_3 + \beta_4Z + \beta_5X_1*Z + \beta_6X_2*Z + \beta_7X_3*Z + e_i$$

Where:

Y = Receipt of Ziswaf funds

α = Constant

β = Regression Coefficient

X₁ = gross NPF

X₂ = Mudharabah income

X₃ = Wadiah Bonus

Z = Company size

X₁*Z = Multiplicative interaction between gross NPF and company size

X₂*Z = Multiplicative interaction between Mudharabah Income and company size

X₃*Z = Multiplicative interaction between Wadiah Bonus and company size

e_i = Error

4. RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Descriptive statistics

The research results used descriptive statistical analysis to assess the characteristics of the data collected. The output can be seen below:

Table 1. Descriptive Statistics

	X ₁	X ₂	X ₃	Y	Z
Means	3.581652	28386.30	27378.27	25082.01	16.65104
Maximum	11.28000	221513.0	558636.0	669879.0	19.58000
Minimum	0.670000	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000	14.12000
Std. Dev.	2.001544	37220.81	64369.17	87500.44	1.474160

Observation	115	115	115	115	115
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Source: Data processed using Eviews by the author

Based on table 1, it was found that the number of research samples was 115 at five Sharia Banks (Bank Muamalat, Bank Syariah Indonesia, Bank Victoria Syariah, Bank Mega Syariah, and Bank Panin Dubai Syariah) during the period 2018Q1 to 2023Q3. In the Gross NPF variable (X_1), descriptive statistics show that the average value is 3.581652, with a maximum value of 11.28000, a minimum value of 0.670000, and a standard deviation of 2.001544.

For the Mudharabah Income variable (X_2), descriptive statistics show an average of 28386.30, with a maximum value of 221513.0, a minimum value of 0.000000, and a standard deviation of 37220.81.

The Wadiah Bonus variable (X_3) has an average of 27378.27, with a maximum value of 558636.0, a minimum value of 0.000000, and a standard deviation of 64369.17.

Meanwhile, for the Moderation Firm Size (Z) variable, the average value is 16.65104, with a maximum value of 19.58000, a minimum value of 14.12000, and a standard deviation of 1.474160.

Finally, in the variable Ziswaf Fund Receipts (Y), descriptive statistics show an average of 25082.01, with a maximum value of 669879.0, a minimum value of 0.000000, and a standard deviation of 87500.44.

Simple Regression Test

Selection of a panel data regression model is an important step in statistical analysis to determine the best approach between *Common Effect*, *Fixed Effect*, or *Random Effect*.

1. Test Chow

This test is carried out to determine which model is the most suitable of the two models *General Effects Model* and *Fixed Effects Model*.

Table 2. Chow test

Effect Test	Statistics	df	Problem.
F cross section	16.035324	(4.106)	0.0000
Chi-square cross section	54.416868	4	0.0000

Source: Data processed using Eviews by the author

From table 2, the Chow test output indicates that the cross-section chi-square probability value is 0.0000, which is smaller than 0.05. This indicates that in this test, the best model to use is the Fixed Effect Model (FEM).

2. Hausman test

Hausman test to determine which model is most suitable from *the Fixed Effect Model* and *Random Effect Model*.

Table 3. Hausman test

Test Summary	Chi-Sq. Statistics	Chi-Sq. df	Problem.
Random cross section	64.141297	4	0.0000

Source: Data processed using Eviews by the author

From table 3 presented, the Hausman test output shows a probability value of 0.0000, which is smaller than 0.05. So, it can be stated that in this test, the best model to use is *the Fixed Effect Model*.

Classic assumption test

1. Multicollinearity test

Table 5. Multicollinearity Test

	X ₁	X ₂	X ₃
X ₁	1	-0.002403	0.044714
X ₂	-0.002403	1	0.203448
X ₃	0.044714	0.203448	1

Source: Data processed using Eviews by the author

From table 5, the output of the multicollinearity test shows that all correlation values between independent variables are below 0.85. This indicates that in the research data there is no multicollinearity problem between the independent variables.

Regression Analysis Data Panel

Panel data regression analysis using the best *Fixed Effect Model* is shown below:

Table 7. Fixed Effect Model Panel Data Regression Analysis Test

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistics	Problem.
C	-1502027.	246902.3	-6.083488	0.0000
X ₁	3507.807	3363.011	1.043056	0.2993
X ₂	0.436765	0.217993	2.003574	0.0477
X ₃	-0.079608	0.095536	-0.833282	0.4066
Z	90344.29	14625.70	6.177092	0.0000

Source: Data processed using Eviews by the author

Moderated Regression Analysis (MRA)

Moderating variables are variables that have the ability to strengthen or improve the relationship between the independent variable and the dependent variable. The following is the test output from the moderation regression analysis:

Table 8. Moderation Regression Analysis Test

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistics	Problem.
C	-922518.8	275453.5	-3.349091	0.0011
X1	5749.326	35848.10	0.160380	0.8729
X2	-10.08100	3.161498	-3.188677	0.0019
X3	4.068197	1.686218	2.412616	0.0176
Z	56587.65	16255.86	3.481062	0.0007
X1Z	-258.7567	2303,884	-0.112313	0.9108
X2Z	0.573503	0.169121	3.391093	0.0010
X3Z	-0.250162	0.102599	-2.438261	0.0165

Source: Data processed using Eviews by the author

Statistic test

1. t test

The t test is used to ask whether the dependent variable partially has a significant influence on the independent variable. Apart from that, this test is also used to determine whether the influence of each independent variable on the dependent variable is significant at the 95% confidence level, with a significance level of 0.05 or an error rate of 5%.

Table 9. T test

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistics	Problem.
C	-922518.8	275453.5	-3.349091	0.0011
X1	5749.326	35848.10	0.160380	0.8729
X2	-10.08100	3.161498	-3.188677	0.0019
X3	4.068197	1.686218	2.412616	0.0176
Z	56587.65	16255.86	3.481062	0.0007
X1Z	-258.7567	2303,884	-0.112313	0.9108
X2Z	0.573503	0.169121	3.391093	0.0010
X3Z	-0.250162	0.102599	-2.438261	0.0165

Source: Data processed using Eviews by the author

Referring to the t test (partial) carried out in this research, the output obtained is as follows:

- 1) Hypothesis 1 (H1): Gross NPF has an influence on Ziswaf Fund Receipts. With a coefficient value of 5749.326 and a probability value of 0.8729, which means it is greater than the significant value of 0.05 or 5%. This indicates that NPF Gross I influences ZISWAF Fund Receipts at Bank Muamalat, Bank Syariah Indonesia, Bank Victoria Syariah, Bank Mega Syariah and Bank Panin Dubai Syariah for the period 2018 Q1-2023 Q3.
- 2) Hypothesis 2 (H2): Mudharabah income has a significant influence on Ziswaf Fund Receipts. With a coefficient of -10.08100 and a probability value of 0.0019, which is lower than the significance level of 0.05 or 5%, this shows that Gross NPF has a significant effect on Ziswaf Fund Receipts at Bank Muamalat, Bank Syariah

Indonesia, Bank Victoria Syariah, Bank Mega Sharia, and Bank Panin Dubai Syariah in the period 2018 Q1-2023 Q3.

- 3) Hypothesis 3 (H3): Wadiah Bonus has a significant influence on Ziswaf Fund Receipts. With a coefficient of 4.068197 and a probability value of 0.0176, which is lower than the significance level of 0.05 or 5%, this shows that the Wadiah Bonus has a significant effect on Ziswaf Fund Receipts at Bank Muamalat, Bank Syariah Indonesia, Bank Victoria Syariah, Bank Mega Syariah, and Bank Panin Dubai Syariah for the period 2018 Q1-2023 Q3.
- 4) Hypothesis 4 (H4): Gross NPF has no effect on Ziswaf Fund Receipts if moderated by Firm Size. With a coefficient of -258.7567 and a probability value of 0.9108, which is greater than the significance level of 0.05 or 5%, this shows that Firm Size is unable to moderate the influence of Gross NPF on Ziswaf Fund Receipts at Bank Muamalat, Bank Syariah Indonesia, Bank Victoria Syariah, Bank Mega Syariah, and Bank Panin Dubai Syariah in the period 2018 Q1-2023 Q3.
- 5) Hypothesis 5 (H5): The influence of Mudharabah Income on ZISWAF Fund Receipts is moderated by Firm Size. With a coefficient of 0.573503 and a probability value of 0.0010, which is smaller than the significance level of 0.05 or 5%, this shows that Firm Size has the ability to moderate the influence of Mudharabah Income on ZISWAF Fund Receipts at Bank Muamalat, Bank Syariah Indonesia, Bank Victoria Syariah, Bank Mega Syariah, and Bank Panin Dubai Syariah in the period 2018 Q1-2023 Q3.
- 6) Hypothesis 6 (H6): Wadiah Bonus has an influence on Ziswaf Fund Receipts which is moderated by Firm Size. With a coefficient of -0.250162 and a probability value of 0.0165, which is smaller than the significance level of 0.05 or 5%, this shows that Firm Size has the ability to moderate the influence of the Wadiah Bonus on Ziswaf Fund Receipts at Bank Muamalat, Bank Syariah Indonesia, Bank Victoria Syariah, Bank Mega Syariah, and Bank Panin Dubai Syariah in the period 2018 Q1-2023 Q3.

2. F Test

The F test is used to find out whether together the independent variables have a significant effect on the dependent variable. Following is the F test output.

Table 10. F test

Problem (F-statistics)	0.000000
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Source: Data processed using Eviews by the author

The F test in this study uses a significance level of 0.05 or 5%, with the criterion that if the F significance value is less than 0.05, then the regression coefficient is considered suitable for use. The F test output in table 10 shows an F significance value of 0.000000, which is lower than the significance level of 0.05. So, it can be stated that simultaneously, Gross NPF, Mudharabah Income, and Wadiah Bonus have an influence on ZISWAF Fund Receipts.

3. Coefficient of determination test

The coefficient of determination is used to show how much the independent variable in the regression model contributes to explaining variations in the dependent variable.

Table 11. Coefficient of determination test results

Adjusted R-squared	0.576378
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Source: Data processed using Eviews by the author

Referring to table 11 of the panel data regression test output on ZISWAF Fund Receipts as the dependent variable, the Adjusted R² value is 0.576378. This indicates that 57.64% of the variation in ZISWAF Fund Receipts can be explained by Gross NPF, Mudharabah Income, and Wadiah Bonus. Meanwhile, the remaining variation can be explained by other variables not included in the regression model.

The Influence of Gross NPF on ZISWAF Fund Receipts

Referring to the test output in Table 9, the probability for NPF Gross is 0.8729, which exceeds the value of 0.05. The test output also shows a positive direction, with a coefficient of 5749.326 and a t-statistic value of 0.160380. So, it can be stated that Gross NPF does not have a significant impact on ZISWAF Fund Receipts. With these results, the hypothesis proposed by the researcher, namely H₁: The Influence of Gross NPF on ZISWAF Fund Receipts, cannot be accepted.

The findings of this research are in line with the results of previous studies conducted by Hadi (2021) Hypothesis testing on Non-Performing Financing (NPF) for Zakat was rejected because the probability value was above 0.05, namely 0.4221.

The Effect of Mudharabah Income on ZISWAF Fund Receipts

Referring to the test output in Table 9, the probability value for Mudharabah Income is 0.0019, the test output shows a value smaller than 0.05. Moreover, the direction of the effect is negative, with a coefficient of -10.08100 and a t-statistic of -3.188677. Thus, it can be stated that Mudharabah Income has a negative impact on ZISWAF Fund Receipts. This indicates that the hypothesis proposed by the researcher, namely H₂: The Effect of Mudharabah Income on ZISWAF Fund Receipts, is supported or accepted.

The findings of this research are in line with the results of previous studies conducted by Wirawan et al. (2022) Mudharabah Revenue, as a form of investment that involves giving capital in the hope of making a profit, it can be considered as one way to manage and return zakat funds in a way that is profitable for the giver of capital and the community that receives it. benefit from these funds. In the context of ZISWAF Fund management, the use of Mudharabah Income can have a positive impact on economic development and community empowerment. This is because Mudharabah Income can create innovations in the management of zakat funds, such as investing in projects that are profitable for the community and returning capital with significant profits. This can increase the receipt of ZISWAF funds and enable the use of zakat funds for productive activities, such as providing training for home industries, providing business capital, and providing scholarships to support quality education, as part of contributing to the development of educated human resources for the nation

The Effect of Wadiah Bonuses on ZISWAF Fund Receipts

Referring to the output test from Table 9, the probability value for the Wadiah Bonus is 0.0176, which is smaller than 0.05. The test output also shows a positive direction, with a coefficient value of 4.068197 and a t-statistic of 2.412616. So it can be stated that the Wadiah Bonus has a positive influence on ZISWAF Fund Receipts. With these results, the hypothesis proposed by the researcher, namely H₃: The Effect of Wadiah Bonuses on ZISWAF Fund Receipts, is accepted.

The findings of this research are in line with the results of previous research conducted Novianto (2021) in a short period, Income (Gross Domestic Product/GDP) and Wadiah Savings Bonus Level have a positive effect on Wadiah Savings in a short

period of time. However, in the long term, Income (Gross Domestic Product/GDP) and the Wadiah Savings Bonus Rate have a negative impact on Wadiah Savings in the Indonesian sharia banking sector. Even though it indirectly discusses the influence of Wadiah Bonuses on ZISWAF Fund Receipts, this research shows that the level of bonuses can influence customer behavior in saving in sharia banking, which in turn can have an impact on the management and use of zakat funds, including ZISWAF Funds. This is because sharia banking is often a source of zakat funds, and customer behavior in saving can influence the amount of funds collected and distributed.

The influence of Gross NPF on ZISWAF Fund Receipts with firm size as Moderation

Referring to the test output from Table 9, the interaction probability between NPF Gross and profitability is 0.9108, which is greater than 0.05. The coefficient obtained is -258.7567, with a t-statistic of -0.112313, indicating a negative direction. With these results, it can be stated that company size does not increase the influence between Gross NPF and company size. So the hypothesis proposed by the researcher, namely H4: Company size can moderate the influence of Gross NPF on ZISWAF Fund Receipts, cannot be accepted.

The findings of this research are not in line with the results of previous research conducted by Katharina et al. (2022) Company size can influence how the company manages and uses zakat funds, especially in terms of investment and development. The influence of Gross NPF on ZISWAF Fund Receipts moderated by company size can be interpreted as how the economic welfare of a country (as measured by Gross NPF) influences the way companies manage and use zakat funds, taking into account the size of their company. For example, companies with a larger scale may have the skills to manage zakat funds more efficiently and effectively, which in turn can increase the receipt of ZISWAF Funds

The Influence of Mudharabah Income on ZISWAF Fund Receipts with company size as Moderation

Referring to the test output in Table 9, the probability of interaction between Mudharabah Income and profitability is 0.0010, which is smaller than 0.05. The test results also show a positive direction, with a coefficient of 0.573503 and a t-statistic of 3.391093. These findings indicate that company size can strengthen the influence between Mudharabah Income and company size. With these results, the hypothesis proposed by the researcher, namely H5: Company size can moderate the influence of Mudharabah Income on ZISWAF Fund Receipts, is accepted.

The findings of this research are in line with the results of previous studies conducted, stating Yuliana (2021) that *company size* can influence the extent to which the company can manage and use mudharabah funds effectively, which in turn can influence the amount of zakat funds collected and distributed.

The Effect of Wadiah Bonuses on ZISWAF Fund Receipts with company size as Moderation

The test results from Table 9 show that the interaction probability between Wadiah Bonus and profitability is 0.0165, which is smaller than 0.05. The coefficient obtained is -0.250162, with a t-statistic of -2.438261, indicating a positive direction. With these results, it can be stated that company size can strengthen the influence between the Wadiah Bonus and company size. So the hypothesis proposed by the

researcher, namely H6: Company size can moderate the influence of the Wadiah Bonus on ZISWAF Fund Receipts, is accepted.

The findings of this research are in line with the results of previous research conducted by Suryani & Fitriani, (2022). Wadiah Bonuses can be considered as one way to manage and return zakat funds in a way that is profitable for both the capital provider and the community who receive benefits from these funds. Effective and efficient management and distribution of ZISWAF Funds has the potential to increase the effectiveness of zakat in achieving community welfare and overcoming poverty problems. The Wadiah Bonus can be considered as one way to maximize the benefits of the zakat funds collected and distributed. In the context of the influence of Wadiah Bonuses on ZISWAF Fund Receipts which is moderated by company size, it can be interpreted that company size can influence the extent to which Wadiah Bonuses can be given and used to manage and return zakat funds. Companies with a larger scale are likely to have more resources to administer Wadiah Bonuses, which in turn can increase the receipt of ZISWAF Funds.

The simultaneous influence of Gross NPF, Mudharabah Income and Wadiah Bonus on ZISWAF Fund Receipts

Referring to the test output from Table 10, it can be stated that the variables Gross NPF, Mudharabah Income, and Wadiah Bonus have a significant influence on ZISWAF Fund Receipts. This is proven by the significance value of 0.000000, which is smaller than 0.05. These results indicate that Gross NPF, Mudharabah Income, and Wadiah Bonus together influence ZISWAF Fund Receipts. So the hypothesis proposed by the researcher, namely H7: Gross NPF, Mudharabah Income, and Wadiah Bonus simultaneously influence ZISWAF Fund Receipts, is accepted. Apart from that, the coefficient of determination or R Square shows a value of 0.576378. This means that 57.64% of the variation in ZISWAF Fund Receipts can be explained by Gross NPF, Mudharabah Income, and Wadiah Bonus. Meanwhile, the remaining 42.36% is influenced by other variables not included in this analysis. So, for further studies, you can consider adding other independent variables to explain greater variations in ZISWAF Fund Receipts.

5. CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

This research leads to several important findings. First, gross NPF does not have a significant influence on ZISWAF Fund Receipts. Second, Mudharabah Income shows a significant negative influence on ZISWAF Fund Receipts, which means that an increase in mudharabah income can result in a decrease in ZISWAF fund receipts, and vice versa. Third, the Wadiah Bonus has a significant positive influence on the receipt of ZISWAF funds, which means that an increase in the Wadiah bonus can increase the receipt of ZISWAF funds, and vice versa.

In addition, the moderating interaction variable shows that company size cannot moderate the effect of gross NPF on ZISWAF fund receipts. However, company size can moderate the influence of mudharabah income and wadiah bonuses on ZISWAF fund receipts.

For further studies, it is recommended to consider using other variables as moderating variables, such as *Return on Assets* (ROA). In addition, this research can expand the scope of the subject by not only paying attention to the Sharia Commercial Bank sector, but also other Sharia Business Units, so that the research findings can represent the entire Islamic financial institutions sector. (Ramadhani, Sukardi, et al., 2022) (Murniyasih et al., 2022) (Ramadhani, Wahyuningsih, et al., 2022) (Ramadhani et al.,

2024).

CONCLUSION

Research result This show that Receipt of ziswaf funds affect CAR significantly significant. which mean that if mark Reception increase then CAR will decrease low, and vice versa. In other words, Return on assets has impact significant negative to CAR; if return on assets is generated high, that is will produce CAR decreases, and vice versa. Next, during interaction variable moderation, Firm size is not can control influence a Receipt of ziswaf funds on sector CAR finances in 2018–2023. Additionally, firm size does not can control the influence of return on assets on mark company sector finances in 2018–2023.

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